
WHO IS ODUDUWA?

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Abstract

Up till today, there seems to be an unending controversy about the personality or character of Oduduwa the founder of the Yorùbá dynasty. A particular school of thought agreed that Oduduwa was among the gods who by the order of Olodumare descended to this earth through a chain lowered from heaven. Another school of thought agreed that the Yorùbás sprung from Lamurudu one of the kings of Mecca whose offspring were Oduduwa the ancestor of the Yorùbás, the kings of Gogobiri of the Kukawa, two tribes in the Hausa country. This paper is out to harmonize conflicting stories.

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Introduction

The Name Oduduwa

The name Oduduwa contains three linguistic morphemes. ODU-DA-IWA. ODU which is the first morpheme means a strongly guarded secrecy in Yorùbá. The next morpheme, DA, literally means to create while the final morpheme IWA, indicates existence. The sum total meaning in ODUDUWA therefore means the body of secrecy or power that creates existence. The principle of vowel coalescence in Yorùbá language will help to explain how DA-IWA finally became DUWA as pronounced.

This claim is further supported by one of the albums released by Olanrewaju Adepoju a popular Yorùbá oral poet which referred to the Yorùbá

people as "OMO ODÙ TÓ DÁ ÌWÀ" meaning son of odu that creates existence.

The Personality of Oduduwa

The only available record of the description of the physical feature of Oduduwa is contained in Adeoye (2005) which claimed that Oduduwa was a tall man with both white and black colour. And to this author, Oduduwa has white complexion like a white man from head to toe, on the right side and the colour of a black man from head to toe on the left side.

He further explained that that was why he usually appeared in black cloth for war and white cloth on religious outings.

The Myth of Origin

Prominent traditional accounts of Yorùbá origin suggested that Oduduwa was the son of Olodumare whom he (Olodumare) sent down from heaven to come and create the earth. For example, Stride (1969) wrote that:

One tradition of origin is a mystical creation legend which intimates that the Yorùbá were the original inhabitants of Ife area. At the dawn of times, the world was a watery waste. On the order of his father the supreme god Olorun, Oduduwa climbed down a chain from the sky. He brought with him a handful of earth, a cockerel and a palm-nut. He scattered the earth upon the water and it formed the land at Ile-Ife ...

This story is repeated virtually in all the available legends of the origin of the Yorùbá people including verses of Ifa corpus. Investigating a mythical situation is nothing short of probing into the obscure and so it may not be actually rational to start here to ask questions on why and how things happened in a legend.

As to when Oduduwa actually lived, there is archeological evidence of fact that there was life around Ife even as far back as 9000 years B.C. The skeleton of a man exhumed at Iwo Eleru in the suburbs of Akure, Thurstan Shaw (1975:112), in a book titled: Discovering Nigeria's Past reported the discovery as follows:

The report shows that our Iwo Eleru man belongs to the negroid group, although somewhat different from the present inhabitants of the area, and it is important piece of evidence in the attempt to unravel the problem of origin of the negroid people of Africa which remains something of a mystery. In fact this skeleton is probably the oldest recognizable negroid skeleton found in Africa. At any rate we can say that the Iwo Eleru man is the most ancient Nigeria yet discovered.

Going by this record, we can start to recognize the fact that life had existed in the environs of Ife, even before the advent of Christianity or Islam.

History of Origin

A parallel account of the origin of the Yorùbá people also pointed to Oduduwa as the father of the Yorùbá race. In this account, Oduduwa is recognized as an individual who hailed from the East. Johnson, S. (1921:8) in The History of the Yorùbás reported that:

The Yorubas are said to have sprung from Lamurudu one of the kings of Mecca whose offspring were: Oduduwa the ancestor of the Yorùbá, the king of Gogobiri and of Kukawa two tribes in the Hausa country.

From the information gathered by Major Duhan and Captain Clapperton from Sultan Bello of Sokoto who founded the city in the late eighteenth century, Clapperton also wrote that:

The inhabitant of this province (Yorùbá), it is supposed, originated from the remnant of the children of Cannan, who were of the tribe of Nimood. The cause of their establishment in the West of Africa was, as it is stated in consequence of their being driven by Yor-rooba son of Kahtan, out of Arab's to the Western Coast between Egypt and Abyssinia. From that spot they advanced into the interior of Africa till they reached Yorùbá where they fixed their re-evidence ...

The account given by Stride (1969) corroborated this report and throw more light into it. It goes as follows:

Oduduwa was the son of Lamurudu, sometimes described as a ruler from the East, sometimes as a Prince of Mecca. When Islam was introduced into his homeland, Oduduwa refused to forsake the religion of his ancestors and he and his supporters were expelled from their native land. After long wandering, they settled among the forest people and founded the state of Ife. Oduduwa had seven close descendants.

In a somewhat similar report, Nwubiko (1982) wrote that:

Oduduwa the chief ancestor and the first king of the Yorùbá, settled at Ile-Ife. His oldest son and successor, Okanbi, died at Ile-Ife leaving seven children. The first was a daughter, the mother of Olowu, the ancestor of Owu. The second also

a daughter was the mother of Alaketu the founder of Ketu. The third became the king of Benin, the fourth Orangun, became the Chief of Sabe and the sixth Olupopo, became his Chief of the Popo and the seventh, Oranmiyan became the founder and first Alaafin of Oyo.

The traditional legend of creation linking the name Oduduwa with the creation of the whole universe may not be scientifically tenable because of the numerous mysteries that attended the creation story. If Oduduwa had actually lived from that early stage of life, it will be really impossible to involve him in the history of Islamic religion of the years AD. This is why it may be outrightly impossible to marry the two incidences of both the creation and migration stories.

All the same, we are still confronted with such questions as to when actually did Oduduwa reign as king in Ife and of what tribe was his subjects. To answer the first question, we may need to once again go back to the year before Christ because there are ample evidences to show that the Yorùbá people had existed in the West of Nigeria from the ages of the biblical Old Testament.

Prominent among the documentary that confirmed the age long occupancy of the land where the Yorùbá people now sojourn is the *Sunday Punch* edition of June 13th 1999 on page 9 which made a clarion call on Chief Segun Osoba, the then Governor of Ogun State, urging him to protect the Sugbon shrine at Ijebu Ode, which British scientists say could be the graveyard of the celebrated Queen of Sheba who visited King Solomon in the Old Testament. The report said that British scientists working with renowned archeologist, Patrick Darling recently ended investigation into the earthworks made up of a wall and ditch which measured 14 metres high and over 160 kilometers.

In a similar development, Ekpo Eyo, contributing to a book edited by Thurstan Shaw in 1975 also reported that:

In the Western State, there are several monuments, which include the three Oshun shrines at Osogbo, the shrine figure of Igbajo and Sugbon's shrine and rampart at Ijebu Ode. Sugbon's credo or shrine, according to Peter Lloyd is eighty miles of rampart encircling an area of four hundred square miles. These 400 square miles (643 sq. kilometres) represents the area of Ijebu kingdom. Modern legend attributes the construction of the ramparts to a wealthy woman called Sugbon who because she had no children caused the rampart to be built so that she could be remembered thereafter. The Muslims of Ijebu Ode who believed that Sugbon married Solomon, pray at the supposed shrine during the Id-el-Fitri instead of the prayer ground.

The evidence adduced above are serious facts establishing the existence of the Yorùbá people on this native land long before the birth of Christ.

If truly Oduduwa and his group did actually migrate from Mecca on purely Islamic crises, it will be difficult to accept him as the ancestral father of the whole of Yorùbá race that had existed for thousand of years before the founder of Islamic religion.

If it was the religious crises of Islamisation that pushed Oduduwa out of Mecca, we may rightly suggest that he, Oduduwa, entered Nigeria during or after the period of Prophet Mohammed. If that is the case, he must have

arrived with his kinsmen the Yorùbás but definitely to be received and hosted by a tribe yet unknown. That is the tribe that originally occupied the land. It is when we are able to ascertain the story of migration and link it with the purported religious war that it will be easy for a research to link the reign of Oduduwa with a particular period in history.

Oduduwa Among Other Yorùbá Deities

Popular Ifa chantations had variously referred to Oduduwa as someone who descended to the world from heaven by means of chain. The attribute also belong to all other gods and deities of Yorùbá beliefs. The attribute could not have been anything but a metaphorical expression of the visitation of the Orisas to the earth.

Virtually all these Orisa's actually came to the world in form of man and died but because of the super human prowess exhibited by the individual during their life, they became deitified after death and their followers became their first worshipers.

Sango hailed from the wife of Sango hailed from Irá in the suburb of Offa in Kwara State. ?sanyin was a native of Isaba near Ikole. Esu the deity descended from Ketu and so were all other notable gods in the history of Yorùbá religion. Even Ifa the oracular god had his origin traced to Oke Igeti in Ife. He also had a father and a mother.

There is little wonder too that Oduduwa, a man of great valour from the east might have led a group of the Yorùbás to this part of the world, settled among the original inhabitants of the land and set up his own powerful kingdom therein it is not unlikely too that this newly formed kingdom swelled above the existing tradition and after the demise of Oduduwa the founder of the new dynasty, he acquired larger followership and was deitified.

Conclusion

This paper is not out to condemn any of the existing account of the position of Oduduwa as the ancestor of the Yorùbá people but an attempt to disregard some of the anomalies created by the mysteries attending the myth and legend of world creation.

It is an attempt at ascertaining the exact period of the reign of Oduduwa and to establish the fact that if truly Oduduwa had migrated from the East at a period quoted in history, he could not have met the areas of Ife occupied which, by implication, will mean that the team that arrived with Oduduwa could not have been the first people to occupy the land. Another significant fact is that it is yet to be proved substantially that the Yorùbá language has either direct or indirect relationship with the Arabic language which is supposed to be the original language of the Yorùbás.

Oduduwa was a great ruler that started the dynasty of Obaship among the Yorùbá tribe. He is hitherto regarded as the forefather of all crowned kings in Yorùbá land till today.

This paper is conclusively calling for further academic research into the history of the reign of this great ruler and father of a great kingdom.

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